

Researcher Well-being in the Context of Fieldwork Studies

E. Mümine Barkçin, Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies Department of
Social Research Methodology, Ankara, Turkey

e-mail: emuminebarkcin@gmail.com

Assoc. Prof. Dr. İlknur Yüksel-Kaptanoğlu, Hacettepe University Institute of Population
Studies Department of Social Research Methodology, Ankara, Turkey

Indicate your track:

(Underline the track, which suits your abstract the most. You can select more than one track)

1. Scientific and practitioners' research presentations
 - a. Bottom-up and community-driven interventions
 - b. Institutional interventions and policies
 - c. Policy-Level insights
2. Workshop/hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Maximum length: 1000 words

All abstracts must be between 500 and 1000 words excluding title, references and tables/graphs. Names and institutions/organisations of authors should not be included in the text of the abstracts to facilitate the blind peer review process but entered separately in the online system.

Purpose

When research ethics is mentioned, the first thing that comes to mind is the rules which are acknowledged to protect the participants. Behind this, is the scientists and researchers who have misused their scientific power in the past. Protecting participants is a crucial and necessary part of research ethics, however, one aspect which is ignored is the researchers themselves. Researchers who adopt the role of interviewer in fieldwork studies risk themselves physically and emotionally by interacting with people one on one. In addition to this, whether it is the participants, the subject of the research or the environment in which the fieldwork takes place, there are numerous situations that also put researchers' wellbeing at risk. The recent years have seen the discussion that researcher wellbeing is indeed an ethical responsibility for researchers themselves and also for the institutions. The main purpose of this study is to understand the fieldwork experiences and how the participants (are) prepare(d) and support(ed) for the challenges of the process.

Design

Adopting both interpretive and critical approaches, this study, which is a part of an ongoing PhD research, is based on qualitative data generation via semi-structured in-depth interviews with researchers, supervisors, and members of research ethics committees. The participants are chosen on the basis of whether they have worked in a fieldwork in the last 5 years, and they are from the fields of social, health and educational sciences. It is our design to conduct in-depth interviews with 30 participants and so far, 4 of them are finished with researchers. I will discuss the preliminary findings of this study regarding the experiences of the participants, mostly about their wellbeing during fieldwork and how they are supported to maintain it, but also what lacks in supporting researchers and what can be done to change this situation into something that creates a healthier “workplace” for researchers.

Results (if applicable)

The themes that have become prominent after the preliminary analysis are classified as *empathy*, *autonomy*, and *engagement in the research*. It is important to state that these themes are interrelated. Empathy is an essential concept, especially for qualitative researchers; however, it might also lead to secondary trauma or compassion fatigue if the subject is more challenging, or the study group is a vulnerable, marginal group. The conflict the researcher faces is between the need of being empathetic during fieldwork but also having to deal with its side effects, which can go as further as losing motivation altogether. It is important for researchers to learn to handle this conflict and get necessary training and/or consultation for that. Although it should be kept in mind that the methodological approach each researcher adopts can be different, and the ontology and epistemology of each approach impose different stances on the researcher. In this case, empathy is shaped by where the researcher puts herself/himself within the hierarchy of the researcher-participant relationship.

Autonomy is conceptualized as having power over decisions that are made regarding the research (process) and stands out as a strong component regarding researchers’ wellbeing during fieldwork. With proper guidance from their supervisors, researchers are well confident in their skills to carry out the fieldwork for their thesis research. On the other hand, working in a project with more researchers and a coordinative team consisting of supervisors might topple the researchers’ autonomy as they are expected to follow certain team rules and have less say in how to conduct the interviews or taking initiative in changing certain questions in the guidelines. Moreover, working towards set deadlines rather than managing their own time can

also affect the wellbeing of researchers as the fieldwork might involve long hours with multiple interviews a day.

Researchers' engagement in the research is another important dimension for their wellbeing. It is seen that engagement is strong when it's their research, as expected, because they have the autonomy to choose what subject to work on and have higher motivation to see the research through. As for projects, it becomes more important for the researcher to be curious about the topic the project is about. Incidentally, perceiving the research as a job might sometimes have a negative effect on researchers' motivation to keep going with their roles, and the project can be seen as something to be done with. Nevertheless, if the needs of the researchers are properly met in these projects, this negative effect might reverse. So, strong institutional support looks like an efficient solution. This is especially important during fieldwork where researchers try to convince the people to participate or collaborate for the research. It is important to note that these themes emerged from the 4 in-depth interviews conducted so far. As the fieldwork continues, the analysis is expected to be enriched and the themes to be varied.

Implications

The preliminary analysis shows and approves the need for a strong personal and institutional support mechanism which helps the researcher to sustain their wellbeing for the challenges they may come across during fieldwork. Therefore, studying towards a standard support mechanism which can empower the researchers regarding their wellbeing seems plausible and in line with ReMO's manifesto.

Acknowledgments

This article is based upon work from the ReMO COST Action on Researcher Mental Health, CA19117, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

Resources